

Analysis of Reviews on Greek Municipalities to Improve Public Service Delivery and Citizen Satisfaction: A Tool for Co-creation and Co-design

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ABSTRACT

The plethora of digital means of expression available to the general public has provided citizens with the opportunity to share their views and opinions on government services online. Citizen (or customer) satisfaction is determined and influenced by a variety of factors, such as the municipality's environment, operations, document requirements and customer service representative behavior, among others. The main purpose of this study is to create a tool for co-creation and co-design in public service provision by using Natural Language Processing techniques to analyze all the available reviews on Greek municipalities, in order to determine the current status of service quality and customer satisfaction, while also suggesting future improvements that can be derived based on the study results. Five major topics that municipalities must focus on in order to provide services to citizens emerged: "services and processes", "response time and location of municipality", "employees", "communication channels", and "employees' behavior". These five identified topics can be utilized to improve the service provision behind each of them, towards the end-users. In this manner, the citizens can actively participate towards the improvement of processes based on their needs, requirements and expectations.

CCS CONCEPTS

• **Computing methodologies** → Machine learning; Machine learning algorithms; Feature selection;

KEYWORDS

Natural language processing (NLP), Sentiment analysis, Government, Feedback, Digital Government, Co-creation and Co-design, Citizen science, Public service provision, Greek municipalities, Topic modeling

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1 INTRODUCTION

The constant emergence of ICT's and the variety of digital means of expression available to the general public has, among others, changed the manner in which citizens interact with their local governments. The new technologies have provided citizens with the opportunity to share their views and opinions on government services online, which can serve as a valuable tool to shift from the conventional, top-down flow of government services provision to a more inclusive, user-centered approach. Online review platforms can be a low-cost and effective alternative tool to influence user choices (Reimer & Benkenstein 2016) [1], (Mudambi & Schuff, 2010) [2]. With online reviews increasing in number, the availability of this information is also on the rise and a plethora of data is constantly being produced. The influence of online reviews on the web or social media is not to be taken lightly as one can understand the magnitude of positive or negative implications a number of given reviews can cause to the entity under analysis in terms of reputation, publicity, popularity and more. The reviewing system of Google (Google review) is one of the various means of giving the opportunity to online users to organize their opinions and personal experiences and share them with the community and, among others, a point of interest for researchers due to some of its inherent advantages. Some of the advantages accompanying online reviews as data sources include directness, low cost, simple data acquisition and high data availability (Lu & Stepchenkova, 2015) [3], (Li et al. 2018) [4]. Moreover, the non-intrusiveness of online reviews is another benefit which is important for researchers to take into account, as it can serve various purposes of studies related to the comprehension of user preferences, behaviours and other useful patterns.

Citizen (or customer) satisfaction is determined and influenced by a variety of factors, such as the municipality's environment, operations, document requirements and customer service representative behavior, among others. If citizens are aware of the available review procedures of the service they are using, they are much

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more likely to provide feedback regarding their experience with this service. It is also likely that a user is positive about a service but dislikes the service process or, occasionally, a citizen might be dissatisfied with the municipal human resources department’s behaviour. Taking into consideration the aforementioned parameters, it is of importance to take a look into how the new technologies can contribute to user feedback mechanisms which local governments can benefit from, focusing on the case of Greece and municipality-level feedback coming from the citizens. Before moving on to the next Section, it is of value to clarify the related terminology of notions this study aims to contribute to.

As far as the concept of co-creation is concerned, at least within the context of digital transformation, co-creation is identified as an appropriate strategy for transforming services based on the adoption of digital technologies (Dugstad et al. 2019) [5]. On another note, co-production is more about customer involvement during the service production. However, the connection between the two terms cannot be doubted, especially if one considers the provision of public services to the citizens. Both co-creation and co-production have a central focus on the creation of value for the entity they are associated with. Osborne et al. (2016) [6] proceeded to the refinement of a conceptual framework to define the types of value co-created in public service delivery. The conceptualization is shown in Figure 1 below: In this conceptualization, Osborne et al. (2016) referred to four ideal types of value, including the co-creation of value by enabling groups of individuals to improve their life quality (Type I in the Figure), the co-creation of value by meeting various community needs (Type II in the Figure), the co-creation of value through Type I or II activities (Type III in the Figure) and, finally, the co-creation of value through co-production to resolve future challenges (Type IV in the Figure). As supported by Osborne et al. (2016), the co-creation of value is fundamental to public services and it is at the heart of their sustainable development. The significance of co-creation on helping public services to overcome existing challenges is also emphasized by Müller et al. (2021) [7]. “The public sector is facing significant challenges regarding public services provision, including a decline in users’ trust and limited resources. Co-creation promises to foster innovative solutions to provide high-quality services that respond to users’ needs.” (Müller et al., 2021) [7].

A user-centric, inclusive approach can be initiated with the development of co-creation and act as an accelerator for the digital transformation of public service provision. The concepts of co-design, co-creation and co-production were also under discussion by Dudau et al. (2019) [8], although in a different light and in order to investigate further the real value of those concepts applied in a service provision context. This is a necessary procedure to demonstrate, not only the potential beneficial sides of those terms but also to consider the possibility they might be associated with various challenges countering the otherwise very intuitive appeal. Various policy labs around Europe and the world are concerned with developing public services and policies using innovation methods to enhance public engagement (Whicher & Crick 2019) [9]. These approaches include the aforementioned practices with a focus on co-design and co-creation, as well as their combination with technologies such as data science, systems thinking and more. As this area of study is still in its infancy, it becomes apparent that there is

		Locus of co-production		
		Individual service	Service system	
Nature of co-production	Involuntary	I: Co-production	III: Co-construction	Towards the co-creation (or co-destruction) of value
	Voluntary	II: Co-design	IV: Co-innovation	

Figure 1: Conceptualizing co-production for public service delivery (Osborne et al. 2016)

a need for further research in order to ensure fruitful implementations with positive social impact.

In the context of the presented research, Müller et al. (2021) also invite for future studies to be conducted on the implementation of co-creation for public services in terms of strategies, actors and outcomes and, in this light, the presented study aims to make a contribution in this body of knowledge by examining how the concepts of co-creation and co-design of processes could be combined with the new ICT technologies applied in the context of Greek municipalities and their service provision.

Our main motivation for this work is to use NLP and available Google reviews for the recognition of problems, barriers, and opportunities to improve customer services and satisfaction levels for the social good (co-creation). The main contributions of this study are the use of NLP for the co-creation task and recognizing the citizens’ problems related to municipal services from the Greek perspective. The analysis framework of the data is also our contribution to the existing literature. The structure of the presented study is as follows: Throughout Section 2, the authors will present related scientific research conducted in this area and discuss various applications of natural language processing and the utilization of user feedback and reviews to improve government services. Section 3 describes the proposed methodology and steps followed in this research to achieve the results which are, in their turn, presented and analyzed in Section 4. Finally, Section 5 proceeds with some concluding remarks and the possibility for future research directions in the light of this study.

2 BACKGROUND

The notion of analyzing online reviews and using the results as a subjective source of information has already been applied in various areas and contexts, but also conducted under different methodological approaches. Yalcinkaya & Just (2022) [10] conducted a textual analysis in order to gain insight on how customer experience differs between local and chain restaurants. The methodology followed included machine learning techniques and the lexicon-based approach, as well as sentiment analysis to detect customer sentiment

present in the reviews. Afterwards, the reviews were put in categories according to certain dining experience attributes. The data for this study originated mainly from Google Reviews and the results, apart from the conclusions per se, were a good indicator of the rising usefulness of online reviews utilized for such purposes. In another domain, Kroon & Park (2022) [11] analyzed exclusively the negative Google reviews available regarding dental services in the Perth metropolitan area. A descriptive and qualitative analysis of the text led to the identification of a number of themes and sub-themes of patient complaints and the conclusions deriving from this study, even though this was the first study to categorize the complaints under a thematic area, were consistent with the ones of an older study on the subject. In a different light but also based on Google reviews as a main source of data, Pacheco Baldó (2022) [12] investigated the usage of metaphor and verbal irony included in reviews about Spanish and American correctional institutions in order to identify potential cultural differences deriving from the manner of discourse and expression and seeking possible connections with dominant cultural characteristics of groups. One can understand that analyzing Google reviews and applying different methodologies on them goes beyond solely seeking to gain insight on peoples' opinions, but can help achieve a variety of goals and serve many perspectives.

When it comes to municipal challenges and how the public's feedback could be converted and integrated into insightful solutions, a lot of research has been devoted to the investigation of this potential, with various approaches, such as systems mapping and systems thinking serving as tools for this purpose. Pomeroy-Stevens et al. (2022) [13] examined how rapidly-growing urban areas can achieve more efficient prioritization and tackle challenges more effectively by introducing a more strategic approach for active public and relevant stakeholder participation. The need for more circular dynamics of otherwise closed systems is becoming more apparent and pushes forward the traction of notions such as the aforementioned systems mapping and thinking, which focus on more participatory approaches for decision making and problem solving. The research conducted by Pomeroy-Stevens et al. (2022) [13] involved four cities in Asia, for which, evidence-based information assisted in taking into account various success factors (e.g. impact) before making big investments. In a slightly different approach but also related to socially impactful research, Rabiei-Dastjerdi et al. (2022) [14] focused on user-generated data and Google Point of Interest (PoI) reviews in order to help understand better the spatial and cultural parameters of urban areas by making use of machine learning methods and practices.

Moving on to more specific applications of methods such as Natural Language Processing for topic modeling and textual analysis, Herng Leong & Putri Dahnil (2022) [15] performed sentiment analysis on healthcare service reviews in order to classify them according to their predominant sentiment and then apply topic modeling techniques to categorize the findings in their thematic areas. The proposed methodology and system architecture begins with the scraping of the data (Google reviews), then topic modeling is applied in order to identify the service area themes and classify them. To continue, sentiment analysis is performed in order to classify as per the sentiment and, as a next step, the keyword identification stage identifies the most prevalent vocabulary. Finally, a

graphical user interface (GUI) is included to loop back the health service feedback to the users. The information gained from this process and offered back to the user gives them the opportunity to select the medical center of their choice according to the feedback results obtained from the designed system. Another study with a clear focus on using sentiment analysis to measure impact based on public opinion is presented by Silva et al. (2022) [16] and it measures the effect of the COVID-19 pandemic on the hotel sector. This piece of research is using text mining and sentiment analysis on TripAdvisor reviews submitted during the time of the pandemic in order to see what the current user needs and expectations include. On a related note with a different subject focus, Shang & Luo (2022) [17] applied the probability model of topic modeling on online reviews about the Mutianyu Great Wall hiking trail in order to identify important factors which affect the visitors' experience in the place. More specifically, the authors conducted the modeling by utilizing the Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) in order to extract themes (or topics) in the analyzed textual data. Apart from the advantages linked to the visitors' perceptive thinking on the facility, this study could also be of benefit to the stakeholders dealing with the marketing, management and other related preservation activities for this facility.

In light of the aforementioned, related research in this area, it is evident that using and analyzing online reviews as a source of unbiased information has gained significant traction and is already being applied in many contexts and in combination with a variety of scientific methods. The shift from top-down approaches to more user-inclusive ones, as also discussed previously in Section 1, can be a strong indicator that another parametric application of this rationale can be the improvement of government services based on citizens' feedback. To identify gaps in service quality and areas of interest that governments would invest on, it would be fruitful to examine the possibility of taking into account a direct and, in many cases, more reliable and non-forced source of public opinion. In the following Section, the overall proposed methodology to examine municipality service reviews in Greece will be described and analyzed.

3 METHODOLOGY

The overall methodology to solve the underlying research problem is shown in Figure 2. As also supported by Herng Leong & Putri Dahnil (2022) [6] and Shang & Luo (2022) [8], the proposed methodology of this study is a combination of descriptive statistics, natural language processing techniques, topic modeling and a supportive approach for co-creation and public participation in government services improvement procedures.

In more detail, the process initiates with the data gathering through different platforms such as Twitter, customer portals, Google Maps and android store reviews. The authors collected data from around 89 municipalities around Greece. The data consists of the users' positive and negative thoughts towards the service provision by the administration of the Municipalities or, indirectly, by the Greek Government.

3.1 Dataset collection

The dataset was required to perform the analysis in order to detect the issues or positive sides of the municipality’s services in Greece. At the beginning, one hundred (100) municipalities around the states of Greece were shortlisted. Out of those, 89 municipalities had reviews on their Google Map profile. The municipality’s name is searched over Google Maps and then the user reviews are extracted using the API solutions provided by the Google Cloud. A total of 5000 reviews were collected and stored in .CSV format for further analysis. The dataset is then imported into the experiment environment using the Python programming language and the required modules (packages) for the textual dataset. The natural language toolkit (NLTK) was used to perform the textual analysis, such as stop word removal or noise removal from the dataset.

3.2 Exploratory data analysis

An exploratory data analysis is the optimal way to investigate and reveal the sentiment hidden in the data. There are different graphs, charts and statistics used to perform the exploratory data analysis. It is of great importance to keep in mind that, before performing the data exploration, the removal of noise and outliers is critical. Noise in the textual data can exist in the form of stop words, links, punctuations or reserved words (e.g., in Twitter, the RT keyword is used by Twitter to indicate that a particular retweet is a retweet). Furthermore, when collecting data from Google Maps, it was noticed that the word "google translated" was added as noise so this word was removed from the dataset. The stemming and lemmatization techniques were applied to each word in the dataset to improve its quality. In stemming, the word must be transformed to its stem; for example, the word "municipality" must be transformed to the word "municipip." In this study, word clouds, bar charts, Bigram charts, pie charts and topic visualization tools are used to explore the textual data about the municipalities. The purpose of each visualization tool will be described in Section 5 of this article.

3.3 Technologies to explore the dataset

The Python programming language along with the required modules is used to perform the sentiment analysis, feature extraction and topic modeling techniques applied using the Genism and Sklearn modules. A sentiment analysis is also performed to explore the public’s opinion about the services, employees, processes and responses of the municipalities. The negative, positive and neutral comments (reviews) percentage and quantity are represented using the pie chart after having removed the empty or blank comments from the actual dataset. Additionally, topic modeling was applied to the dataset to extract the public’s topics of discussion regarding the municipalities.

3.4 Sentiment analysis, topic modeling and evaluation matrix

After performing the preprocessing, exploratory analysis and feature extraction, the final data frames are used to measure the sentiment of the dataset. Vader is a module in natural language processing that uses an already (ready-made) trained model to predict the classification of the municipalities’ dataset, such as whether the comments are positive, negative or neutral. The predictions

made by the Vader model were used to make the pie charts graph. In addition to being a component of preprocessing during topic modeling, stemming is also performed. For instance, the words "play," "player," and "playing" will be stemmed to "play," which is the original form of the word. After calculating the stem words, the corpus is transformed into a document-word matrix, requiring all words to be lowercase, stemmed and at least three words long. The document-word matrix is identical to the textual dataset’s feature matrix. The sparsity of the document-word matrix will allow for the calculation of the number of non-zero elements in the matrix. The greater the degree of sparsity, the greater the number of non-zero entries and terms in the document-word matrix. The parameters in Equations 1 and 2 are used to figure out how sparse the vector is.

$$Sparsity = \text{percentage of NZ cells} \tag{1}$$

$$Sparsity = (\text{sum NZ entries of document} - WM / SD - WM) * 100 \tag{2}$$

In the preceding equations, NZ is non-zero, WM is the word matrix and SD is the document size. In this instance, sparsity is assessed to be at 78.9%. The document-word matrix, which was built in the preceding phase, is now ready for use. The Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) model for topic modeling will employ the document-word matrix. The parameters of LDA are the number of epochs (iterations) that will be performed to appropriately classify the topics. The maximum number of iterations was set for 5 topics at 20 epochs (iterations). LDA is used to figure out how the five topics are related to the words in the document’s word matrix.

The LDA evaluation matrix is the calculation of perplexity and log-likelihood used to evaluate the model’s performance. The number of topics, perplexity and log-likelihood are the parameters used to calculate the LDA model’s performance. The 5-topic perplexity and log-likelihood values are given in Equations 3, 4 and 5. According to a heuristic, higher log-likelihood values are considered to be preferable for topic modeling using the LDA approach. Lower the value of perplexity value is better for topic modeling.

$$Log Likelihood = -104255.09347172253 \tag{3}$$

$$Perplexity = \exp (-1 * \log - \text{likelihood per word}) \tag{4}$$

$$Perplexity = 205.87958098348585 \tag{5}$$

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Exploratory data analysis

The proposed methodology described in the previous section has been implemented as is and the results are discussed in this section. The dataset was collected from Google Maps reviews using the Google Cloud API and then the data was processed to remove the noise, such as numbers, links, emojis and reserved keywords, which were no longer required in the experimental setup. After cleaning the dataset, the authors used a word cloud to present the words that commonly appeared in the collected dataset. The top 200 words in the dataset are shown in Figure 3. The bigger the size of the word in the word cloud, the more frequently that particular word appeared in the dataset. The words "service", "employee", "helpful", and "people" are the most frequent among the others.

The next visualization, after checking the word frequency, is how words appeared in the dataset in context with the other words.

Figure 5: Sentiment analysis of the Google Reviews

appeared in the dataset. The term bigram refers to the two-word combinations in NLP jargon. To extract the features from the textual data, the Uni, Bi, and Tri gram features are frequently used. After preparing the dataset, the Vader library was used, which is openly available through the Python environment, to measure the sentiment of the collected dataset with respect to three categories. The dataset was passed as a DataFrame to the Vader instance, and it returned the predictions made by each class. Figure 5 depicts the class distribution in the form of a pie chart. Most of the dataset instances were positive, like 41.8% of our dataset. 37.4% of instances were negative, which means these Google reviews contain some negative comments and reviews about the municipalities. In the following description, those specific negative words or topics over which people are dissatisfied will be discovered. The third part of the pie chart depicts the neutral reviews of the dataset, which account for almost 20.8% of the whole dataset. The absolute number of reviews is also mentioned in the pie chart for better understanding. From the negative and positive comments, an attempt to identify the user's needs and their satisfaction level is made. More specifically, the negative reviews might help us figure out what is problematic with the municipality and what the municipality can do to improve the situation.

After finding the sentiment of the Google Maps reviews, the sentiment prediction was combined with the original dataset and the filtering technique used to distinguish the dataset into three parts. For instance, the authors separated the negative, positive and neutral reviews from the original dataset. Figure 6 depicts the negative sentiment class, where words were discussed. The words "employee," "phone," "rude," "unacceptable," "citizen," and "appointment" were discussed the most frequently. One can say that the negative reviews were constituted of these words. This implies that, when one citizen was posting the review on Google Maps, they were possibly dissatisfied with the employee or the phone call at the municipality. In this manner, the relationship between the negative words and the story behind them can be identified. The data, which was positively classified by the model, will be drawn to understand the words inside it. Figure 7 depicts the most frequent words which were part of the positive reviews about the municipality's service, employee or response. However, it is known

from the distribution that most of the reviews were positive and the positive reviews mostly contained the words "good", "employee", "helpful", and "excellent" in them. In this way, the authors showed the most repeated positive words and what the attention of the citizens to these words were. The larger the size of the word, the more frequently it appears in the dataset or reviews. So, words such as "service", "employee", "helpful" and "good" were discussed very often in the reviews.

4.2 Identified topics and subtopics

At this point, after a detailed experiment about the sentiment of the Google reviews, the topic modeling technique was applied to extract the topics from the whole bunch of datasets. The Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) topic modeling methods are used to extract the topics that were present in the dataset. It is extremely important to extract the topics because the negative and positive words in Figures 5, and 6 are known, but now what is needed is to know what the topics were about, where those words were used in the dataset. The LDA method requires that the dataset is in a special format which is achieved by the feature extraction. The stemmed and lemmatized dataset is used to extract the features from it. The bag-of-words vector is generated from the textual data. The bag-of-words is based on the tokenized count of words and their frequencies to generate a unique valued vector in which features will be stored for future experiments. The bag-of-words vector will be used to pass on to the LDA model. The LDA model uses the inputs such as "bag-of-words", "number of topics", "iterations (epochs)", "data chunk size", and random value. The authors set up 5 numbers of topics with 20 iterations and 100 chunk sizes. Table 1 depicts the LDA topic modeling model with the topic number and words associated with each topic. The topics are combined into one major topic based on the words predicted by the LDA model. The final suggested topics are "services and processes", "response time and location of the municipality" "employees", "communication channels" and "behavior of the employees" were the major topics detected from the whole dataset. In order to evaluate the LDA model, the authors used the perplexity and log-likelihood values, as mentioned previously at the end of Section 4.

4.3 Problems and issues identified in the municipalities

The comprehensive analysis based on data published by citizens on Google Maps serves an important purpose in accommodating the future needs of citizens. These reviews have important indicators to help improve the services, employees, processes and communication mechanisms. The use of natural language processing for the review analysis and topic detection from all the reviews and comments is very helpful to get an insight into the data, both technically and artificially, without any induced bias. The reviews or comments played a vital role in improving the problems or long-standing issues in the service delivery field by the municipalities to the citizens. Citizens always want these issues resolved before they interact with a public official again. In a private firm or organization, one negative review may reduce the cost or sales of a product, otherwise known as "word of mouth". The public sector also needs to handle the problems identified in the presented methodology.

Table 1: The topics extracted from the dataset using the Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA)

Topic#	Topics	Final suggestion
1	[service, good, build, well, time, serve, do, go, municipality, fast]	Services and processes
2	[Kind, immediate, need, wonder, square, park, serve, response, ladies]	Response time and location
3	[staff, nice, place, child, always, find, inform, useless, leave, camp]	Employees
4	[phone, people, make, pick, even, answer, thank, call, take, serve]	Communication channels
5	[employee, help, appoint, work, citizen, public, unacceptable, excellent, polite, know]	Employees' Behavior

Figure 6: Negative reviews and the words associated with each review

that was explored was how many datasets were positive and how many datasets were negative. The positive dataset consisted of positive feedback in the form of Google reviews, so, the topics identified based on these positive reviews can also be considered as the best practices which have already been implemented in the municipalities to serve the citizens in the best and timeliest manner. The presented study has implications for local governments, as it provides them with valuable, unbiased feedback on their services and can serve as a guiding point for meaningful decision-making regarding the identified issues. In some municipalities included in the experimentation, where they already have in place the best processes and services, the response time is also justifiable, the employees' behavior is also good and the communications channels are also improved by past experience. Finally, all the remaining municipalities which are getting negative responses from the citizens, need to shift towards improving their services, processes, employees, communication channels and behavior.

Figure 7: Positive reviews and the words associated with each review

5 CONCLUSION

The availability of new technological advances in developed and developing countries has shown that citizens' reviews or comments on a product or public service are the most popular means to improve the product or service in return. The presented study provides an automated framework to analyze the reviews and comments posted on Google Maps after or before visiting the Greek municipalities by Greek citizens or others and suggests improvements and best practices in order to serve the citizens in the best and timeliest manner. The proposed methodology uses natural language processing-based sentiment analysis and topic modeling to highlight the weaknesses and positive aspects of the municipalities by utilizing the feedback of the citizens. Following extensive experimentation, five major topics that municipalities must focus on in order to provide services to citizens emerged. These five major topics, which were highlighted by the citizens in the form of Google reviews, are "services and processes", "response time and location of municipality", "employees", "communication channels", and "employees' behavior". These five topics were detected using the natural language processing method Latent Dirichlet Allocation model. The sentiment of these five topics is also of importance in order to see what citizens are discussing about the municipality's services. The underlying research can be utilized to improve each identified topic and improve the service provision to the end-users. In this manner, the users or citizens can participate in the co-creation and co-design processes based on their needs, requirements and expectations. This study is not exhaustive with respect to the data sources, which means that, in

By using NLP and topic modeling techniques, such as services, processes, response time to applications, communication channels, and employee behaviors, the situation could be further improved.

4.4 Identified best practices in municipalities

The authors' proposed methodology not only explains the problems but also shows the path towards the best practices which could be adopted by the municipalities. For instance, one aspect

a similar manner, it would be possible to add anonymous private feedback or social media such as Facebook, Instagram, or LinkedIn data to highlight or track further problems or issues in the current municipal service provision environment. One more limitation of this study is that the samples collected to conduct this study are not large in number. In the future, this study can be enhanced by applying the same methodology to a larger number of reviews to improve the quality of topic detection.

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